

A Neutrosophic Extension of the Inverse Gamma Distribution: Properties and Applications

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Abstract: This paper proposes a new the neutrosophic inverse gamma (NIG) distribution which is a generalization of the classical Inverse Gamma (IG) model to deal with vagueness, uncertainty and indeterminacy observed in healthcare and survival data. Since the traditional models are limited by rigid fixed parameters and are not capable of well approximating the fact that all imprecision arising from measurement errors, missing values, conflicting expert's assessments should be left in the imprecision of human judgement. The proposed model is more flexible and realistic, since shape and scale parameters can vary in certain intervals, by using neutrosophic logic. Some certain characteristics of the NIG distribution, such as the probability density function (PDF), cumulative distribution function (CDF), and moments are obtained and studied. The estimation techniques are also constructed for neutrosophic data. With simulations, random samples were generated from the model and the model's ability to capture uncertainty in the simulated data is illustrated. Simulated results indicate that NIG is providing more robust and informative parameter estimates as long as sample size increases. Eventually, solar sector industrial data is employed to validate the proposed methodology and highlights its effectiveness in decision making

Keywords: Neutrosophic logic, gamma model, neutrosophic probability, data uncertainty

1. Introduction

Probability and probability distribution theory are the basis of statistical treatment of many datasets that commonly exist in healthcare, industry and survival data to provide a means of understanding and quantifying the uncertainty which is so much a part of random outcomes [1]. In health, data exhibits natural variability related to biological variability among patients, differences across environment exposures and treatment heterogeneity [2]. Probability theory offers a consistent framework through which to represent this variability, allowing clinicians and researchers to model, predict, and compare outcomes including disease incidence, treatment response, patient survival, etc [3]. In the context of survival data, in particular time-to-event data, probability distributions represent the duration until an event of interest, for instance, death, relapse, hospital discharge, recovery. Distributions like exponential, Weibull, Gompertz, log-normal, Cox proportional hazards model are commonly used for their flexibility in accommodating various hazard rate forms (constant, increasing or decreasing over time) [4]. These models enable the estimation of survival functions, hazard rates, and median time to survival which are important in measuring the potency of interventions and clinical decision making [5].

In addition, they prove useful in dealing with censored data, a common phenomenon in survival analysis because the event of interest does not always occur to every subject within the study period

[6]. Probability theory contributes to still ensuring that the statistical inferences retain their meaning and without being too weakened by censoring the observations [7]. Moreover, probability distribution provides the basis for the construction of diagnostic tests as it allows the estimation of sensitivity, specificity, predictive values, which are critical for the effective screening and early diagnosis of diseases [8]. It furthermore facilitates the design and analysis of randomized clinical trial and enables a priori power, sample-size and confidence-interval calculations, making the results valid and reliable [9]. In epidemiology, probability models assist in estimating disease prevalence or incidence, determining the burden of disease, assessing risk factors and predicting future health care needs. The IG distribution is part of the exponential family of distributions with positive support but is seldom considered for modeling positive data because the Gamma distribution tends to dominate [10]. One such difference is in their modes; the mode of the Inverse IG distribution is always positive; the mode of the gamma can be zero. So for low stochastic noise, where the gamma would inappropriately fit an exponential decay to the activation, it can still be used to distinguish the positive activation from the stochastic noise (modeled most typically as a gaussian distribution [11]). It is in this subtle nuance, added to the fact that they have no analytical expressions for their parameter estimate, that underscores the importance of effective algorithms for estimating IG distribution [12]. In statistics, the IG distribution is of fundamental importance, as one of the most used instances of a conjugate prior for the variance of a normal distribution in Bayesian inference [13]. This makes it to be crucial in applications involving the estimation of uncertainty or variability such as, in financial risk assessment, noise modeling for signal processing, and reliability engineering for gauging the spread of failure times [14]. Its interesting property of having exclusively a positive mode further distinguishes it from the gamma distribution, allowing more accurate discrimination between true positives and random noise, especially when signals are weak. This natural capacity for modeling the positive-valued variabilities highlights the significance of the IG to various fields in science and engineering.

The IG distribution is important for healthcare data analysis, especially in situations where parameters such as variance or scale are uncertain as occurs in survival analysis, medical imaging, and Bayesian statistical approaches [15]. It is frequently employed as a prior distribution for variance components in Bayesian hierarchical models that are quite popular for modeling complex health care data involving multiple levels of variation, for example, differences between-patients and differences within patients. For example, in the representation of the variability in patient's response to treatment, or in the progression of some disease, the IG distribution is a flexible and mathematically tractable option to model prior beliefs for unknown variances [16]. In the survival analysis, it can be also used in the Bayesian approach to modeling frailty or unobserved heterogeneity among individuals, enhancing the stability of the hazard rate estimation. Also, in the field of medical imaging, for example in PET and MRI, the IG distribution can be used to model noise and signal variability allowing to obtain more accurate image reconstruction and assessment. It can also be helpful in addressing imbalanced data along with uncertainty in risk estimation when the patient data do not have normal variation. Its conjugate nature supports traveling speed in posterior estimation, especially if it is paired with other distributions such as normal or gamma. The IG distribution is useful, in health economics, for modeling variability in costs in cost-effectiveness analyses [17].

Neutrosophic random variables provide an effective and novel alternative tool to model uncertainty, indeterminacy, and incomplete information associated with the data in the healthcare domain and through some comparison experiments, they dominate classical and fuzzy probabilistic methods in certain criteria [18-20]. Conventional statistical approaches may not be able to effectively capture the vagueness, imprecision, and conflicting information and sources typically found in clinical data such as test results, patient-reported outcomes, and expert opinions particularly in early

stages of a disease or in the context of rare disorders. By utilizing three aspects (truth, indeterminacy, and falsity) in a possibilistic sense, neutrosophic random variables offer a flexible and powerful tool to describe uncertainty more naturally and are appropriate for healthcare researchers and practitioners to fit the reality that we observe data can be partially known, ambiguous, or conflicting [21]. This also has clear and immediate benefits in personal medicine where treatment plans must be made on the basis of partial or contradictory data, but also in epidemiology, where population health data is rife with partial or conflicting records. Neutrosophic models can also help by combining quantitative and qualitative information in an intelligent way and thus assist the decision-making in a complex medical environment [22]. Their indeterminacy-tolerant nature allows them to make predictions that are more reliable than regular models, when standard models break down due to rigid assumptions or to the unavailability of the exact data [23]. In survival analysis, risk estimation and diagnosis assessment works, neutrosophic random variables provide stronger uncertainty analysis, enabling better understanding of patient risk and treatment effectiveness. Furthermore, their superiority is demonstrated as harsh medical conditions of the real world when noise, imprecision and human subjectivity are unavoidable. By taking in account in a precise way the degree of indeterminacy, neutrosophic random variables provide more flexible and resilient statistical conclusions and they can help systems with strong intelligence on health-care systems that are good to cope with system complexity and uncertainty in a more accurate and adapted manner than simpler classical models [24-27].

The IG distribution has exact parameters and is unfavorable to model the uncertainty and vagueness that typically appear in healthcare data. Healthcare data are usually uncertain in terms of ambiguous, incomplete, conflicting information caused by measurement errors, patient variability, expert disagreement etc., or missing information cannot be well represented with fixed parameters of classical model.

To overcome this shortcoming, in this paper, the neutrosophic structure of the Inverse gamma distribution is proposed by considering the indeterminacy aspects in its structure. By generalizing the conventional IG distribution to the neutrosophic domain, the shape and scale parameters of the proposed distribution are both represented as neutrosophic numbers, which results in the ability to model a wide range of uncertainty as seen in real world medical data. This generalization increases the flexibility of the distribution and also yields a more realistic and flexible model for studying complex healthcare related issues like, patient survival, treatment's efficacy and progression of the diseases. Then we can see that the neutrosophic IG distribution can be applied in dealing with the indeterminate phenomenon in clinical data, inform the decision circumstances with more information under vague conditions, and have put forward a new method in medical statistics.

The rest of study is organized as follows: Section 2 presents preliminary results. Section 3 illustrates proposed model and its significance. Section 4 explains the estimation procedure. Section 5 describes real life application of industrial sector. Section 6 concludes the major findings of the work.

2. Preliminary Results

In this part an analytical structure of the truncated normal model has been discussed. The truncated normal distribution is a variant of the normal distribution used in probability and statistics, in which the random variable is subject to lower, upper, or both constraints.

In this section, we describe the classical structure of the IG distribution with some essential properties. A random variable is said to follow the IG distribution if it is represented by the following probability density function (PDF):

$$f(t | \delta, \rho) = \frac{\rho^\delta}{\Gamma(\delta)} t^{-\delta-1} \exp\left(-\frac{\rho}{t}\right), t > 0 \tag{1}$$

Eq. (1) shows that the IG distribution is a two-parameter continuous probability distribution often utilized to model positive-valued random variables, especially in Bayesian statistics as a prior for variance parameters. It is the distribution of the reciprocal of a gamma random variable.

The geometrical structure of the PDF is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 PDF of the IG distribution for different values of parameters.

The PDF of the IG distribution, which describes the probability of observing different values of a positive-valued continuous variable, given a specific hyperparameter, often employed for instances in which smaller values are more typical, but larger values are also possible. The PDF is extremely flexible in its shape, which is controlled by its two parameters, the shape and scale. When the shape parameter is less than one, the distribution is strongly skewed, with a long tail for larger values and a much higher peak in the proximity of zero. As the value of ρ increases, the distribution becomes more balanced and less skewed. This generality makes the IG distribution applicable to modelling in a situation where outcomes are strictly positive but highly variable, such as risk assessment, Bayesian statistics, and to accommodate uncertain variances in financial data.

Like PDF, the other function is cumulative distribution function (CDF) which can be written as:

$$F_T(t) = \int_0^t f_T(u) du = \frac{\Gamma(\frac{\rho}{t})}{\Gamma(\delta)} = 1 - \frac{\gamma(\delta, \frac{\rho}{t})}{\Gamma(\delta)} \tag{2}$$

Figure 2 CDF of the IG distribution with different parameters setting

The CDF of the IG distribution is used to find the probability that the random variable will take a value less than or equal to a particular value. It begins at zero and incrementally approaches one as the value of some variable increases. The slope of the CDF depends on the shape and scale values. For lower values of the shape parameter the CDF rises slowly at first, meaning that low values are more likely, before becoming steeper towards higher values. The steeper proportion of the CDF in the middle range at higher shape values indicates greater peak. This property further underscores the usefulness of the IG distribution CDF for evaluating cumulative probabilities in uncertain environments, for example in reliability analysis, Bayesian inference, and financial risk analysis. The average of a probability distribution is a basic statistic that represents the expected or average value of a random variable. It represents a focal value that there is a tendency for the data to be located in close proximity and is very important to make predictions, comparisons, decisions in different areas that include science, economy, engineering and others. For IG distribution, its expected value can be written as:

Mean:

$$E(T) = \frac{\rho}{\delta - 1}, \quad \text{for } \delta > 1 \tag{3}$$

Similar to mean other related property is the variance of the random variable. In case IG distribution, it is given by:

Variance :

$$\text{Var}(T) = \frac{\rho^2}{(\delta - 1)^2(\delta - 2)}, \quad \text{for } \delta > 2 \tag{4}$$

The variance of the IG distribution indicates how much a random variable's values are spread out from the mean. It exists only when the shape parameter is sufficiently large, indicating that the distribution

becomes more stable and less variable as this parameter increases. To see further the importance properties of IG distribution, it is important to derive the kth moment of the IG distribution which is given by:

Kth moment:

$$\mu'_k = E(T^k) = \frac{\rho^k \Gamma(\delta - k)}{\Gamma(\delta)}, \quad (5)$$

Based on Eq (5), the shape coefficients of the IG distribution can be written as:

$$\text{Skewness} = \frac{4\sqrt{\delta-2}}{\delta-3}, \quad \text{for } \delta > 3 \quad (6)$$

Skewness coefficient of the IG distribution represents the asymmetry of the shape of distribution. This distribution is right-skewed, that is, it has a long right tail. The majority of the point data is clustered close to the lower bound while some slightly larger values are stretched out to the right. The amount of skewness is related to the value of the shape parameter i.e., the smaller this parameter, the more skewed (and hence more asymmetric) the distribution. When the shape parameter increases, the distribution becomes more symmetric, and the skewness is reduced. Being aware of this kind of behavior is important when it comes to working with data that exhibits very high uncertainty or very high extreme values.

The kurtosis coefficient is also related to shape of the distribution, and it is given by:

$$\text{Kurtosis} = \frac{30}{\delta-4} + 3, \quad \text{for } \delta > 4 \quad (7)$$

The kurtosis parameter of the IG distribution indicates how thick its tails are and how peaked it is relative to a normal distribution. It is well known that IG distribution has in general high kurtosis implying that its tails are heavier and its peak sharper. This means the data has more chances for extreme values or outliers. The degree of kurtosis is a function of the shape parameter i.e.; smaller shape parameter values result in more heavy tails and a sharper peak. The distribution is increasingly moderate with respect to the peak and tails as the shape parameter increases. This property is beneficial to analyze the data that is susceptible to only rare, but important, deviations

3. Neutrosophic Inverse Gamma Distribution

In this section, we provide the parallel neutrosophic structure of the IG distribution so it may be able to handle uncertainty or vague information that commonly exist in processing data. Now in the neutrosophic structure the parameters of the IG distribution are assumed to follow in interval form rather than crisp values. The PDF of the NIG distribution is given by:

$$f_N(t | \delta_N, \rho_N) = \frac{\rho_N^{\delta_N}}{\Gamma(\delta_N)} t^{-\delta_N-1} \exp\left(-\frac{\rho_N}{t}\right), \quad t > 0 \quad (8)$$

The neutrosophic form of the IG PDF is also a generalization of the classical density function. In the classic mode, the distribution has two fixed numerical parameters: A shape parameter, δ_N and a scale parameter, ρ_N . These parameters are employed to characterize the distribution explicitly.

The neutrosophic PDF with different parameter settings is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3 PDF of the NIG distribution with imprecise parameters

The given parameters in the neutrosophic setting are not, however, fixed numbers. But not actual numbers, just ranges or fluctuations. That means we don't know the precise values that they take, but we do have a range on which we know that they fall. This enables us to represent uncertainty, indeterminacy or information incompleteness in the data in real life more, showing a wider applicability. Therefore, the corresponding neutrosophic PDF (as shown in Figure 3) does not supply a definite output for a point, but a range to which the value at the given point belongs, due to the uncertainty of the parameters. This approach is employed when data or model parameters are not exactly known or are vague, which can happen, e.g., in engineering reliability analysis, fuzzy risk modeling, or rough measurements.

Similarly, the CDF of the proposed model with neutrosophic form can be written as:

$$F_N(t | \delta_N, \rho_N) = \frac{\Gamma(\delta_N, \frac{\rho_N}{t})}{\Gamma(\delta_N)} = 1 - \frac{\gamma(\delta_N, \frac{\rho_N}{t})}{\Gamma(\delta_N)}, \quad t > 0 \tag{9}$$

The visibility of CDF in neutrosophic environment can be seen in Figure 4.

Figure 4 CDF of the NIG distribution with imprecise parameter values

The CDF of the IG distribution under uncertainty is plotted in Figure 4. In contrast to the usual CDF, which generates a single curve, a shaded band is shown to account for the uncertainty in the distribution parameters. In particular, shape and scale parameters are not constant but are described by intervals, which express the vagueness or unambiguity of information in the data or in the model. The lower and upper dashed lines in Figure 4 represent the minimum and maximum case (minimum/maximum values of parameters). The shaded area between these lines shows all attainable cumulative probabilities resulting from a combination of the used parameter values of these intervals. This neutrosophic representation can accurately take into account the uncertainty as is the case in the practice, by a graphical analysis parameter changes can be inferred how the behavior of the distribution is changing with time.

Now mean of the NIG can be expressed as:

$$E_N(T) = \frac{\rho_N}{\delta_N - 1}, \quad \text{for } \delta_N > 1 \tag{10}$$

Here ρ_N and δ_N represent the neutrosophic (interval-valued) parameters, and the result is also an interval expressing the possible range of mean values under parameter uncertainty.

The neutrosophic variance can be expressed as:

$$\text{Var}_N(T) = \frac{\rho_N^2}{(\delta_N - 1)^2(\delta_N - 2)}, \quad \text{for } \delta_N > 2 \tag{11}$$

The variance of the IG distribution represents the spread or variability of the distribution. If we take fixed values of the shape and scale parameters, then it is given, in the classical setting, only when the shape parameter is more than two. These parameters are, however, not exactly known in the neutrosophic framework; they are expressed as intervals to illustrate an element of doubt, vagueness, and ambiguity. Therefore, the variance is not even an (absolutely) constant value but is rather bound to some range. It gives a more versatile and realistic measure of imprecision in such cases when the exact nature of the distribution is not precisely known.

The shape coefficients in neutrosophic structure can be established as:

$$\text{Sk} = \frac{4\sqrt{\delta_N - 2}}{\delta_N - 3}, \quad \text{for } \delta_N > 3 \tag{12}$$

$$\text{Kurt} = \frac{30}{\delta_N - 4} + 3, \quad \text{for } \delta_N > 4 \tag{13}$$

In the neutrosophic setting, the shape parameter is not given as a constant, but it is considered as an interval, in order to model uncertainty or limited knowledge about the system. Consequently, neither skewness nor kurtosis can be expressed by unique value but only ranges that describe the potential range in the distributions shape resulting from this parameter uncertainty. The neutrosophic skewness provides a range that reflects how the skewness of the distribution may change according to actual

value of the shape parameter in its uncertain zone. In the same way, the neutrosophic kurtosis gives a set of values in which the tail behavior of the distribution could be modified between the bounds of the uncertain parameter. These neutrosophic moments provide a realistic and flexible modelling technique for the application in which data is uncertain, imprecise, incomplete or vague.

Now by assuming the different values of neutrosophic parameters we may calculate the basic characteristics of the proposed models. Results based on given values of neutrosophic parameters are given in Table 1.

Table 1 Neutrosophic moments of the proposed distribution

Case	δ_N and ρ_N	Mean Interval	Variance Interval	Skewness Interval	Kurtosis Interval
1	[4.10,5.00], [1.50, 2]	[0.37, 0.64]	[0.04, 0.19]	[3.46, 5.26]	[33, 303]
2	[5.20, 6.00], [1.00, 1.50]	[0.20, 0.35]	[0.01, 0.04]	[2.66, 3.25]	[18., 28]
3	[6.50, 7.50], [2.50, 3.00]	[0.38, 0.54]	[0.03, 0.06]	[2.08, 2.42]	[11.57,15.]
4	[5.50, 6.50], [1.20, 1.80]	[0.21, 0.40]	[0.01, 0.04]	[2.42, 2.99]	[15, 23]
5	[4.50, 5.20], [2.00, 2.50]	[0.47, 0.71]	[0.07, 0.20]	[3.25, 4.21]	[28, 63]

Table 1 provides the statistical details of the NIG distribution. Each row corresponds to a different case, and the two key parameters of the distribution are not actual fixed values but in a certain range. These heuristic parameters account for the fact that either the dynamics of the modeled system are not accurately known, or the system properties are not fixed and evolve over time. For each case Table 1 provides the range of the values taken by four significant characteristics of distributions: the mean, dispersion, skewness and kurtosis. The input parameters are intervals, and the measures should also be intervals signaling the minimum and maximum values that these features can accept. This neutrosophic gateway has a rich source of flexibility and good realistic interpretation for modelling the behavior of the distribution based on the inclusion of uncertain or incomplete information. It allows decision makers to examine a range of exact outcomes rather than rely entirely on a single point estimate.

4 Estimation Method

In this section we will discuss the estimation procedure for unknown parameters in the proposed model. The most common method is Maximum likelihood (ML) approach for finding the unknown values. The ML approach is a simple statistical method which is meant to estimate the parameters of a probability distribution from observations by maximizing the likelihood function. This function is probability of observing the data given a certain set of parameter values. In a nutshell, MLE is looking for such parameter values that make the observed data most probable. Closed-form solutions for all parameters of more complicated distributions sometime not available. Nevertheless, despite being biased, in practice ML is used extensively for its good properties, such as consistency, efficiency, and asymptotic normality, so that it constitutes a powerful tool in the theory and application of statistics.

The log-likelihood function in neutrosophic environment can be written as :

$$\log L(\delta_N, \rho_N; t) = n\delta_N \log \rho_N - n \log \Gamma(\delta_N) - (\delta_N + 1) \sum_{i=1}^n \log t_i - \rho_N \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{t_i} \quad (14)$$

Maximizing $\log L(\delta_N, \rho_N; t)$ with respect to ρ_N is given by:

$$\widehat{\rho}_N = \frac{n\delta_N}{\sum_{i=1}^n t_i^{-1}} \tag{15}$$

Maximizing $\log L(\delta_N, \rho_N; t)$ with respect to δ_N yielded iterative expression:

$$\delta_N^{(t+1)} = \Psi^{-1} \left(\log(n\delta_N^{(t)}) - \log \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{t_i} \right) - \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \log t_i \right) \tag{16}$$

Eq. (16) shows that the expression is not closed form so some numerical procedure will be required to find solution. Other than ML approach we can use method of moment to find its solution easily.

$$\bar{t} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n t_i \tag{17}$$

$$s^2 = \frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{i=1}^n (t_i - \bar{t})^2 \tag{18}$$

Now utilizing method of moments logic, we can write:

$$\widehat{\delta}_N \approx \frac{\bar{t}^2}{s^2} + 2 \tag{19}$$

$$\widehat{\rho}_N \approx \bar{t} \left(\frac{\bar{t}^2}{s^2} + 1 \right) \tag{20}$$

Thus, we can utilize Eq. (19) and Eq. (20) to find the values of unknow parameters.

Now utilizing Eq. (9) the quantile function for generating random samples can be written as:

$$t = \frac{\rho_N}{Q_{\text{Gamma}}^{-1}(1 - u; \delta_N)}$$

where Q_{Gamma}^{-1} is the inverse CDF of the gamma distribution. A simple R program can be utilized to draw random samples at selected values of parameters.

The table presents 40 interval-valued random samples generated from the proposed distribution, where the shape parameters ρ_N and δ_N are treated as intervals: $\rho_N \in [2.5, 3.5]$ and $\delta_N \in [4.0, 6.0]$. For each sample, a uniform random number from uniform distribution was generated, and the quantile function of the IG distribution was applied.

The lower bound of each interval was calculated using the lower parameter values (ρ_L, σ_L), while the upper bound was computed using the upper values (ρ_U, σ_U), resulting in random intervals $[t_L, t_U]$ that reflect both data variability and parameter uncertainty. Results are shown in Table 2

Table 2 Random samples from the proposed distribution

Random samples				
[1.291, 1.406]	[3.304, 3.057]	[1.582, 1.668]	[4.581, 3.972]	[6.425, 5.187]
[0.707, 0.837]	[1.928, 1.967]	[4.785, 4.111]	[2.007, 2.034]	[1.711, 1.781]
[7.485, 5.844]	[1.701, 1.773]	[2.543, 2.471]	[2.083, 2.097]	[0.874, 1.006]
[4.964, 4.233]	[1.199, 1.320]	[0.695, 0.824]	[1.383, 1.490]	[7.303, 5.733]
[4.720, 4.067]	[2.626, 2.537]	[2.362, 2.326]	[18.335, 11.611]	[2.433, 2.383]
[2.717, 2.608]	[1.982, 2.012]	[2.165, 2.165]	[1.295, 1.409]	[0.979, 1.110]
[8.046, 6.182]	[5.027, 4.276]	[2.614, 2.527]	[3.371, 3.107]	[0.622, 0.747]
[1.772, 1.834]	[3.054, 2.869]	[1.134, 1.258]	[1.361, 1.470]	[1.167, 1.290]

Results in Table 2 show that random values are in interval forms due to assumed uncertainty in the parameters of the proposed distribution. These results will be converted to classical results with zero uncertainty. Now if we draw the random samples with same parameters settings from the proposed distribution and estimate the results using Eq (19) and Eq. (20), values of estimated parameters across various sample sizes are given in Table 3.

Table 3 Estimated parameters of the proposed distribution using MM metod

Sample Size	$\widehat{\delta}_N$	$\widehat{\rho}_N$
25	[4.5933, 6.0044]	[7.6475, 10.3654]
50	[2.9302, 3.6441]	[6.9044, 8.0100]
100	[3.5693, 4.6989]	[6.2727, 8.4560]
150	[3.1906, 4.1232]	[5.6735, 7.4104]
200	[2.5906, 3.3737]	[4.1973, 5.6146]

The obtained values of the parameter's estimation for the NIG distribution based on MM method for different sample sizes are given in Table3. When the sample size enlarges from 25 to 200 the interval estimates of the parameters tend to become more stable and narrower. This trend suggests that the estimating method gets more accurate as the dataset gets bigger. For smaller sample sizes (e.g.25) the estimates exhibit wider (larger) intervals demonstrating larger uncertainty as little information was available. On the other hand, with bigger sample sizes, such as 200, the estimated intervals are much closer to the expected parameter ranges, indicating the robustness as well as the reliability of the method with more observations.

5 Real Data Application

In this section the proposed distribution has been implemented on temperature data with connection to solar industrial data. The data is reported and has been in the study [28]. Solar renewable energy harnesses the power of the sun to enable sustainable industrial development and stands as an effective and affordable alternative to fossil fuels. In any country where the installation of solar energy systems is being optimized, data on temperature cannot be overlooked. Accurate temperature patterns help determine ideal panel placement, efficiency rates, and maintenance needs, ensuring maximum energy output. It improves energy security as well by boosting system performance, which in turn reduces the dependency on non-renewable sources and results in a socio-economic benefit by cutting costs and generating new jobs and eventually leading to sustainable energy-based industrial growth. Solar power helps in cutting greenhouse gas emissions if embraced widely as it is a way of generating green energy and also restraining environmental degradation which subsequently can alleviate some global climate change efforts. Solar power allows the energy industry to innovate in areas such as energy storage, smart grids, and decentralized generation systems that invariably improve the reliability and overall efficiency of all aspects of life (use cases). Its broad scale from residential, commercial rooftops, to large solar farms, affords industries the opportunity to broaden their energy mix, cut down operational costs as well as gain energy independence. Also, as per the report, solar industry advances job creation, boosts investment and fosters a vibrancy in the clean energy sector making it an ideal substance for sustainable economic growth and industrial development. The study [28] has been carried out to determine the climate and weather patterns of Al-Kharj region in order to address the suitability of Al-Kharj region for governmental solar projects expansion using neutrosophic Rayleigh model. The climate in Al-Kharj is hot desert, with an average annual temperature of 27.5 °C (81.5°F), almost 0.49% higher than the national average in Saudi Arabia. Average annual rainfall is 8.82

mm in 20.4 days and represents some 5.59% of the year. The data is explained and available in the aforementioned source. However, to utilize it for our proposed model, its histogram is provided in Figure 5.

Figure 5 shows monthly neutrosophic temperature intervals for the region of Al-Kharj. A shaded band between the two curves indicates the neutrosophic uncertain region. The lower curve is for minimum monthly temperatures and the high one is for maximums. The shaded region demonstrates the range of temperatures over all months, emphasising a sharp rise during summer and a notable fall during winter, reflective of the subtropical desert climate regime that exists here. By utilizing Eq (19) and Eq (20) the unknown values can be estimated as:

$$\widehat{\delta}_N = [4.21, 44.35] \text{ and } \widehat{\rho}_N = [35.16, 1671.27]$$

Figure 5 Neutrosophic data of temperature data for Al-Kharj region

These estimated values can be utilized to different characteristics of the proposed distribution. These wide estimated intervals reflect substantial uncertainty between lower and upper data bounds, capturing the variability in temperature-related measurements across the Al-Kharj region. This shows proposed model provide more flexibility and reliability as compared to existing model.

6 Conclusions

In this paper, we proposed a new generalization of the classical IG distribution which is obtained after incorporating the neutrosophic logic into its framework, known as the neutrosophic inverse gamma (NIG) distribution. This novel statistical distribution is particularly designed to tackle the uncertainties that typically arise within industrial applications. A primary advantage of the NIG distribution versus the classical approach is its ability to reflect parameter uncertainty by using interval-based shape and scale parameters that are more suitable to capturing ambiguity and imprecision in industrial contexts. The model preserves important statistical properties, while generalizing their use to environments with uncertainty, and therefore makes them more interpretable and flexible. Some essential statistical characteristics of the proposed model have been discussed. Estimation strategies such as the MM method and ML method were successfully extended to the neutrosophic framework and were demonstrated, via simulations. Numerical results provide more accurate estimates as the sample size increased. In conclusion, the NIG distribution shows a great promise in the advancement of statistical modelling and inference in complex data environments involving vague, incomplete or contradictory information. The application of the proposed model to temperature data in connection with solar industry potential for Al-Kharj region demonstrates its strong suitability for scenarios where precise uncertainty modeling is crucial, as it offers a comprehensive framework for effectively addressing uncertainties in industrial decision making.

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